

**«IMPROVING WAY OF THINKING OF LEARNERS IN THE EXAMPLE
OF NATIONAL FAIRY TALES»**

Sattorova Shaxlo Axadovna¹

¹Teacher of Shaxrisabz State Pedagogy Institute,

Ismatov Asliddin Fazliddin o'g'li²

²Teacher of Uzbek State of World Languages University,

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the significance of fairy tales for the kids of kindergarten age. Besides, with the example of the theories of some story writers it is emphasized that it is very important to listen to fables and myths for children to have a better outlook and imagination.

Key words: Fairy tale, lesson, development, education, thinking, vocabulary, literature.

A fairy tale is an amazing tool for working with the inner world of a person, whether it is a child or an adult, a powerful tool for development and gaining experience. A fairy tale can provide keys for entering into reality in new ways, it can help a child to learn the world, to understand his own experiences. Long since life experience was transmitted through figurative stories. Children climbed on the stove, grandmothers spun and told fairy tales, instructive stories, knowledge of life accumulated in the baby's memory. Unfortunately, this experience is lost. In our "fleeting" time, an adult has no time to read, tell a tale to her baby, and not just read, but comprehend - what does she teach? what life lesson is hidden in it? The child more often sits at the TV, at the computer. He draws all the baggage of life values from the media, computer games, and not from books. So we end up with a "person" with a "distorted" inner world that can solve problems with the "absence" of the heart. In our life we often meet with various problems and difficulties. Adults are looking for ways to solve them, but what about children, whose life experience is so small? What to do baby? - Tell him a fairy tale! At preschool age, children rapidly develop their imagination, which clearly reveals itself in the game and when perceiving works of art, especially preschool children like fairy tales. The fairy tale occupies such a strong place in the life of a child that some researchers call the preschool age the age of fairy tales. In older preschool children, empathy is immediate: they present themselves with their favorite characters in the works, penetrate into the inner world, copy their character. So they get used to the image that with the help of imagination they become participants in the events, for example, the fate of a bunny driven out of its hut by a fox, children try on their own and, sympathizing, think something like this: "What would I do if someone ousted me

from home? «. The tale plays an important role in the aesthetic development of children of preschool age, without which the nobility of the soul, sensitivity to someone else's grief and suffering is inconceivable.

The fairy tale teaches children to dream, to emphasize the most important thing, the individual in the image, to summarize the essential features, strengthens mental activity. Fairy tale is always pedagogical, it is used as a means of educating the best human qualities. The tale enriches the inner world of children, they are drawn to it. A fairy tale for a child is nothing but a means of comprehending life, a way of knowing, understanding some life phenomena, the moral attitudes of society. The fairy tale is a universal developmental educational tool, bringing the child beyond the directly perceived, immersing him in possible worlds with a wide range of models of human behavior and orienting them, providing a rich speech environment. As Yu.A. Lebedeva rightly noted, "any fairy tale is oriented towards a social and pedagogical effect:" it teaches, educates, warns, teaches, encourages activity, and even treats ". Flerina, E.A. noted such a feature as the naivety of children's perception, children do not like a bad end - the hero must be successful, because the child, as a rule, puts himself in his place, acts mentally, fights his enemies. We can safely say that fairy tales play a large role in the development of the child's personality.

The famous Italian storyteller Gianni Rodari wrote the book «Grammar of Fantasy», where he described techniques that promote the development of children. D. Rodari emphasized that «children remain conservative with regard to fairy tales; they do not want to change anything in them, insisting that the fairy tale be told in the same way and almost in the same words.» Then, in his opinion, there comes a moment when the need is born for new impressions of the old fairy tale. And then the children come up with a new end for her or endow the hero with new properties, which contributes to the development of coherent speech in children, understanding the ability to select words with a similar or opposite meaning. It should be emphasized that the sensual side of the child's perception of the work in no way diminishes the role of language and thinking and, especially, the artistic word that leads the child along the lines of sensually - figurative and abstract thinking. Leushin A.M. rightly asserts: "A visual representation of the situation of a story or a fairy tale is created through an understanding of the context, the semantic content of words and those speech constructions with which the author or narrator draws his thought. So the child gets used to translate contextual speech into the language of visual images, and he, too, is learning little by little to express the images of his own

ideas and experiences with the help of developed, structurally shaped contextual speech. « Thus, the fairy tale creates in the child a need for a new structure of speech, and its form gives the necessary samples for this, which he develops during his development. Flerina, E.A. It also speaks about the expediency of using fairy tales for the development of coherent monologue speech of preschoolers. She believes that “Russian folk tales are the best example of the form of storytelling, on which both the storytelling technique and the construction of the story should be learned: a clear line of development of the action, a clear, simple structure, dynamics in the deployment of the action, a small number of characters, bright, economical and contrasting images, rhythm and sonority of the language. « If we compare the tale with other literary works, then its undoubted advantages will be seen. For example, the myth. He also speaks the language of images, but he is pessimistic, and children do not like bad ends, so they do not perceive the myth as a story about something interesting and exciting. The moral of the fable, its moral character, is more suitable for an adult than for a child. Children understand that, for example, they cannot do this, but the fable does not answer the question «Why?». In the fairy tale, the reason for which this or that principle should be guided is clear. If we compare the fairy tale with a realistic story, it becomes clear that it is psychologically improbable for the child, since his thinking is still unprepared to perceive reality in its purest form. A literary work should attract the attention of a child, arouse his curiosity, enrich life, stimulate his imagination, develop intelligence, help him understand himself, his desires and emotions, and also express it all with words.

A child, working with a fairy tale, first of all satisfies three basic basic needs (singled out by I. P. Yanichev):

1. the need for autonomy (independence);
2. the need for competence (strength, omnipotence);
3. the need for activity.

The result of meeting these needs is the formation of a number of personality qualities of a child - a preschooler:

- the desire to express their personal opinions, to defend their interests and views;
- ability to own initiative in communication, to manage the process, to respond emotionally;
- social competence.

The value of fairy tales lies in their influence on the child’s all-round development, and especially on moral education. Fairy tales inspire confidence

in the triumph of truth, the victory of good over evil. As a rule, the sufferings of a positive hero and his friends are temporary, temporary, joy usually comes after them, and this joy is the result of the struggle, the result of joint efforts. In order for a child to grow up as a good person, it is necessary to work with him, starting from early childhood. Fairy tales help to revive spirituality, mercy and humanity in people. And we must begin with children, since the material side of life has already captured them into their networks. Children can still sympathize, empathize. The task of the preschool institution is to prevent these sprouts from being crushed by the reality of a tough life, but to do everything necessary so that they grow, deeply germinate in the soul and heart of a child.

The main means of education is literature for children, fairy tales that turn human hearts to good, generosity, conscience, honor and justice.

The personality of the child begins in childhood. Therefore, the sooner literature, namely a fairy tale, touches the strings of the child's soul, and not just the mind, the more guarantees that good feelings will take over evil ones in them. After all, literature is a pounding heart, speaking in the language of feelings. The lessons that a fairy tale gives are lessons for life for both large and small.

References:

1. Miller, Martin A. the foundations of modern terrorism: state, society and the dynamics of political violence. Cambridge University Press,2013.
2. Nairn, Tom; James, paul (2015). Global Matrix: Nationalism, Globalism and State-Terrorism.london and New York:Pluto Press.
3. Stern, Jessica. The Ultimate Terrorist. First Harvard University Press Pbk. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard University Press,2000. cop.1995
4. Terrorism, Law and Democracy; 10 years after 9/11. Canadian Institute for the Administration of Justice.

